

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable Report

Deliverable: D8.5 EOSC integration activities report (final)

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Disclaimer

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NEANIAS is a project that comprehensively addresses the ‘Prototyping New Innovative Services’ challenge set out in the ‘Roadmap for EOSC’ foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community’s research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

NEANIAS develops thematic services for EOSC communities in the field of Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. The integration of the thematic services into the EOSC ecosystem together with the investigation of the possibility of onboarding a number of core services to EOSC as well are among the main project targets to pursue, thus exceeding the targets initially set for the availability of NEANIAS services on EOSC marketplace. Furthermore, the reuse of EOSC services for the purposes of NEANIAS services is another key challenge of the project towards EOSC integration.

This deliverable presents the results of EOSC integration activities realised by the time of its preparation. It also highlights the remaining EOSC integration activities expected to be completed until the end of the project.

1. Introduction

NEANIAS is an EU funded project, which aims to develop and integrate services to EOSC in the field of Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. The objective of integration is to share these thematic services with scientific researchers of EOSC communities on these fields.

This deliverable reports on the accomplishments of NEANIAS activities towards EOSC integration as they were realised by the time of its preparation. It also highlights the EOSC integration activities expected to be completed until the end of the project. The report updates and complements the information presented in Deliverable D8.4 “EOSC integration activities report (interim)” [1], elaborated in December 2021. The latter presented the progress of EOSC integration activities at that time, also comparing it against the plan presented in Deliverable D8.3 “EOSC integration plan (final)” [2], elaborated in August 2021. At the time of writing this deliverable, the project has already onboarded ten (10) thematic services to the EOSC Marketplace (TRL7 or greater), while the onboarding of one more is in progress (expected to become available on EOSC marketplace in July 2022). At the same time, the project has completed the onboarding of three (3) core services to EOSC, while the onboarding of one more is under investigation.

This deliverable has been written based on the current EOSC landscape, which is a continuously evolving environment, and provides up-to-date information as regards several fields related to EOSC integration, such as architecture, application programming interfaces (APIs), access mechanism, federated services and so on.

The structure of this document is as follows: Section 2 makes a brief introduction to the targeted EOSC integration activities, as these were presented in Deliverable D8.4 of the project. Section 3 presents the results of EOSC integration activities at the time of writing this deliverable and highlights current plans for additional activities to be completed until the end of the project. Finally, the conclusions are presented in Section 4.

2. Integration plan to EOSC

2.1. NEANIAS services to be integrated to EOSC

The following section introduces the NEANIAS services that are/will be integrated into EOSC. These services cover three major research sectors; Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. Beyond these thematic services, NEANIAS develops/provides Core services in four (4) groups; C1 covers Open-Science lifecycle support services, while C2 covers EOSC hub, RIs and cloud integration enabling services, C3 covers AI and C4 covers Visualization services. C1 and C2 provide basic services to enable integration of the thematic services in NEANIAS, i.e. not services targeting reuse by 3rd parties, therefore they will not be onboarded to EOSC and as such they are not presented in detail in this section. On the other hand, the C3 and C4 services support the delivery of NEANIAS thematic services, and their integration to EOSC is optional, based on the plans of the respective providers.

2.1.1. NEANIAS thematic services

2.1.1.1. Underwater services

Underwater surveys have numerous scientific and commercial applications in the fields of archaeology, geology, biology, and energy involving tasks such as ancient shipwreck prospection, ecological studies, environmental damage assessment, and detection of temporal changes. NEANIAS has developed the following underwater services that are already available to EOSC:

- **U1 - Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data**

The UW-BAT (Bathyprocessing) service provides a large number of MB-System tools to post-process vendor specific raw data. Its approach is to create digital terrain models (DTM) and maps from multibeam echosounder (MBES) raw data.

- **U2 - Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data**

The Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data (UW-MOS) service deals with optical mapping in underwater environments. UW-MOS provides an operational solution for large area representation of the seafloor also addressing visibility limitations from the underwater medium.

- **U3 - Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data**

The Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data (UW-MAP) service delivers a user-friendly cloud-based solution integrating cutting-edge machine learning frameworks for mapping several seabed classes, validated for archaeological, geo-hazards, energy, and other applications.

2.1.1.2. Atmosphere services

NEANIAS Atmosphere services aim to address operational studies related to the atmosphere and engineering tasks to involve diverse user communities linked to the atmosphere. The sectors they target include, among others, meteorologists, industrial air pollutant emitters, ecologists, rural urban planners and air quality authorities, geohazards, civil protection, insurance or health agencies. NEANIAS has developed the following atmosphere services:

- **A1 - Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring**

The Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring (ATMO-FLUD) service provides a set of algorithms for the calculation of flux densities of Sensible Heat, Latent Heat, Turbulent Kinetic Energy and other scalars like GHGs. The input data to the service is user provided although test data are available for trial runs. Real data should be experimentally obtained by the user bearing in mind that the fundamental method employed in this service is the “Eddy Covariance”.

- **A2 - Monitor atmospheric Perturbations and Components in Active Tectonic Regions**

A2 service consists of two sub-services; the ATMO-SEISM and the ATMO-STRESS services.

- ATMO-SEISM is a service for scientists to design, develop and test the correlation between gas measurements, atmospheric conditions and earthquake data.
- ATMO-STRESS shows regional trends on 2-D gridded map (x-y plane) and can reconstruct a paleostress trajectory map by implementing the following two different methods (Lee and Angelier, 1993): (i) polynomial and (ii) distance weighted interpolation.

- **A3 - Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting**

The Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting (ATMO-4CAST) service allows the generation of meteorological forecasts by using the Weather Research and Forecast Model.

2.1.1.3. Space services

The Space services deliver a springboard of tools to enrich the workflows of a wide range of targeted users from academic/research institutions to industrial stakeholders, e.g. aerospace engineering and related technology companies, but also national space agencies and public outreach bodies, e.g. space museums and planetariums.

The latest NEANIAS release includes seven services tailored to the Space sector user requirements and driven by three clusters of common functionalities, i.e.: S1 - FAIR Data Management and visualization for complex data and metadata, S2 - Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional images, S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques:

- **S1 - FAIR Data Management and Visualization for Complex Data and Metadata**

S1, namely “SPACE-VIS” services, provide an integrated operational solution for astrophysics and planetary data management aided by advanced visualization mechanisms, including visual analytics and virtual reality, and it is underpinned by FAIR principles.

The **ViaLactea** service accesses astrophysical surveys to aid understanding of the star formation process of the Milky Way. ViaLactea Visual Analytics (VLVA) combine different types of visualization to perform analysis by exploring correlations managed in the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB). VLKB includes 2D and 3D (velocity cubes) surveys, numerical model outputs, point-like and diffuse object catalogues and allows

for retrieval of all available datasets as well as cut-outs on the positional and/or velocity axis.

The **Astra Data Navigator (ADN)** is a virtual reality environment for visualizing large stellar catalogues. The first prototype has been customised to access cloud services for interactive data exploration and navigation with the ability of exploring advanced virtual reality mechanisms providing full immersion.

Finally, the **ADAM-Space Service** (Advanced Geospatial Data Management platform) accesses a large variety of environmental data and is customised in NEANIAS to access planetary data.

- **S2 - Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional image**

S2, namely “SPACE-MOS” service, provides tools for making high quality images from raw data (map making) and for assembling such images into custom mosaics (mosaicing).

The **AstroMapMerging** service exploits Montage (<http://montage.ipac.caltech.edu/>) and it is integrated with VLKB for merging adjacent datasets.

The ISIS3 and ASP under **ADAM-DPS** service allows integration with data processing pipelines in ADAM which offers tools for planetary data analysis and for producing cartographic products, such as Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) and 3D models from stereo imagery.

- **S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques**

S3, namely “SPACE-ML” service, provides advanced solutions for pattern and structure detection in astronomical surveys as well as in planetary surface composition, topography and morphometry. The service integrates cutting-edge machine learning algorithms to perform automatic classification of compact and extended sky structures or planetary surfaces.

CAESAR service allows to extract and parametrize compact and extended sources from astronomical radio interferometric maps. The processing pipeline consists of a series of distinct stages that can be run on multiple cores and processors.

AstroML service has been developed to integrate a deep learning mechanism to significantly improve source identification, classification, and characterization of sources in large-scale radio surveys.

The **Latent Space Explorer (LSE)** service performs unsupervised representation learning of astronomical images using deep learning techniques (e.g., autoencoders) and interactive visualization of the representations with the chance to apply clustering methods in order to help the domain expert to understand the structure of the representation space.

2.1.2. NEANIAS core services

2.1.2.1. C3 Artificial Intelligence services

C3 Artificial Intelligence services form the upper level of core services in the NEANIAS ecosystem and provide facilities that may reach up to the end user offering features of a typical Machine Learning (ML) workflow lifecycle, and that are also intended for composition of higher-level services. The EOSC integration of C3 services is optional; current integration plans and achievements are presented in Section 3.1. NEANIAS is developing the following services in this area:

- **C3.1 AI Science Gateway: service for development of ML models using Jupyter Hub**

A development environment is necessary for the researchers to design, prototype, implement and test AI powered solutions. To serve as a universal core service for multiple users, the popular IPython based Jupyter Hub project is preferred, with TensorFlow and Keras libraries. Researchers are able to prototype solutions, while computationally intense training can be loaded to a computational cluster. Results can be visualized using the Visualization gateway (C4.2).

- **C3.2 Serving trained ML models**

Accessing trained models as web services should be possible seamlessly, with low efforts. To deploy a model as an API, large amount of memory is necessarily allocated and used constantly. Technically, there are multiple approaches to implement model serving, user and researcher-friendliness is prioritized. The fundamental idea behind model serving is that authorized clients are able to access prediction functionality without directly accessing the model, which would create a serious overhead caused by data transfer and memory allocation. Instead, a RESTful API based communication is preferred between a model server and the client. The server implements the model, allocates memory to efficiently handle prediction, and listens for input parameters on the interface. On request, prediction is done using the inner implementation, and the results are responded to the client.

- **C3.3 Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod**

The training of deep neural networks on large amount of data requires a significant amount of processing time, which could be reduced by using GPU accelerators. The next step in increasing the performance is by using multiple GPU-enabled nodes in a distributed environment. While the parallel processing of deep neural networks has its limitations, Horovod [3] is a robust tool which can be used to scale the training of TensorFlow based network implementations.

- **C3.4 Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML**

In addition to models based on neural networks (that can benefit from a multi-GPU deployment, especially for learning phases) that are managed through C3.3, other AI techniques for classification, regression, or clustering tasks can however benefit from a deployment and execution in a distributed and memory-based architecture such as the one offered by Spark. In particular, C3.4 will support a variety of machine learning models such as Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees and ensemble models (Random Forests and Gradient Boosting) for both classification and regression, clustering algorithms, and other support functions that are useful in real-world, large scale, machine learning pipelines. The set of basic ML algorithms and models can also be extended by means of creative parallel computing approaches (e.g. parallel implementations of DBSCAN algorithm on top of Spark, an algorithm which is not natively provided by MLib, are known and available).

2.1.2.2. C4 Visualisation services

C4 services, namely “visualisation services” in the context of NEANIAS, form the upper level of core services in the NEANIAS ecosystem and provide facilities that may reach up to the end user offering features of a typical visualisation workflow lifecycle, and that are also intended

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for composition of higher level services. The EOSC integration of C4 services is optional; current integration plans and achievements are presented in Section 3.1. NEANIAS is developing the following services in this area:

- **C4.1 Framework for Visual Discovery (VD)**

C4.1 provides tools to support data intensive computing for visual scientific discovery (including research training and outreach) for observational data, theoretical simulations and 2D/3D tiling and maps. C4.1 consists of three distinct high-performance services for visual analytics from multidimensional data tables (VD-VisIVO), high-quality volume rendering of particle-based datasets exploiting a variety of parallel programming models leveraging upon heterogeneous infrastructures (VD-Splotch) and creation of interactive 2D/3D tilings and maps (VD-Maps).

- **C4.2 Visualisation Gateway (VG)**

C4.2 provides a development environment for designing, rapid prototyping, implementing and fully testing complex visualisation solutions for realising common data exploration workflows. C4.2 services are envisaged to be interconnected with C3.1 to visualise AI powered solutions, C4.3 to underpin powerful VR/AR solutions and C4.4 to facilitate end-user data accessibility. C4.2 services are deployed in a way that is fully embedded within the relevant workflows of end-user activities, while exploiting diverse parallelisation models and infrastructure accelerator capabilities.

- **C4.3 Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR)**

C4.3 provides a toolkit underpinning an environment for designing, implementing and testing complex visualisation solutions exposed to end-users via Cross Realities (XR) mechanisms, e.g. those based on Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). C4.3 exploits the framework for visual discovery developed in C4.1. C4.3 services are envisaged to be interconnected seamlessly with C4.2 to furnish complex visualisation workflows and C4.4 to underpin advanced data access. As part of the XR toolkit various VR/AR viewers are expected to be realised visualising not only space objects but also 3D data of various typologies of interest to other NEANIAS domains (e.g. atmospheric).

- **C4.4 Spatial Data Stores (DS)**

Spatial data stores allow data to be referenced, queried and retrieved, based on a given location (e.g. the globe, the Earth, planetary bodies with a proper reference system or the sky).

2.2. Targeted EOSC Services for integration

Based on the investigation of the services listed in Section 2.1.1, we identified the following services/support as requirements to integrate the thematic services to EOSC:

- Providers and Service modelling based on EOSC Provider and Resource profiles. This choice aims to facilitate the onboarding of NEANIAS providers and services in the EOSC portal, complying with the existing standards and EOSC guidelines.
- Authentication and authorization
- Monitoring

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- Accounting – As described in D8.3 [2], the EOSC offered Usage Accounting Service primarily focuses on infrastructure level assets and services. The NEANIAS approach to the task, through the NEANIAS Accounting Service takes a more fine-grained approach, letting individual services define their own accountable resources and respective actions.
- Helpdesk – The Helpdesk requirements for the NEANIAS service offerings are addressed through the NEANIAS offered Helpdesk functionality under the Service Management System (SMS) defined processes and tools. Still, the approach taken is chosen so that future integrations with the EOSC Helpdesk remains an option.
- Data Management Planning
- Data Catalogue

In this section, we introduce the available EOSC services in these categories and how and to what extent they will be integrated with NEANIAS services.

2.2.1. EOSC Portal

NEANIAS aims to deliver thematic services to researchers via EOSC, therefore the registration of these services in the EOSC Portal is a compulsory step. EOSC offers an API that allows service providers to push information to EOSC directly from their systems or service catalogues. The use of this API is within our plans since the beginning of this project so as to avoid updating the same information in two different systems; the NEANIAS catalogue portal and the EOSC portal. However, some restrictions on the use of the API arise from EOSC, which necessarily will be respected by NEANIAS; the API cannot be used for the initial registration of a service provider or for the onboarding of the first service of a provider. On the other hand, the API allows the onboarding of additional (i.e. apart from the first one) services of a specific provider and facilitates the update of information of already onboarded services. The administrator of the provider, which wishes to make changes to their data (either provider or resource data), should put its unique token (obtained from the EOSC portal) at the dedicated textbox and thus get the permission to push the new information to both catalogues (NEANIAS & EOSC). To be noted that the administrator should use the same e-mail to login to both catalogues.

2.2.2. Federation Services

In this subsection, existing EOSC federation services, which we plan to directly integrate with the NEANIAS services or have been thoroughly taken into account in order to achieve future integration, are introduced.

2.2.2.1. AAI services

The NEANIAS project includes in its offering the NEANIAS AAI service that offers a horizontal solution for all NEANIAS services to cover the common requirements of authenticated access, whether it comes in the form of a direct user request or as cross service invocations. The NEANIAS AAI service in its core supports identity federation through well-established standards and protocols, including Open ID Connect (OIDC) and SAML.

Using these standards and protocols, the NEANIAS AAI service acts as an integration point with the EOSC Portal offered AAI. This integration will allow EOSC-trusted users to be offered access to NEANIAS resources. As the number of EOSC-trusted identity providers expands, the

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NEANIAS AAI will also expand its reach to a wider user base, regardless of the end user supporting Identity Provider.

This approach also allows the NEANIAS AAI service to extend the network of federation of supported identity providers, providing seamless authenticated access to trusted users via widely used and accepted standards.

Apart though from Authentication, NEANIAS AAI tackles the Authorisation aspect of AAI, for which currently there is no central point where consumers can shape their authorisation approach in the context of EOSC AAI, and the precise policy and approach is handled by NEANIAS AAI and consumer services themselves.

From a technical standpoint, integration with EOSC AAI is straightforward and preparatory steps have been taken. However, EOSC's AAI direction is now applying emerging protocols and their implementations that, although expected and welcome, have not been tested in NEANIAS infrastructure and raise some (minor admittedly) sustainability risk as they are based on modified versions of existing software that may or may not be maintained in long term. What is even more important is that the release timeline of the service to be compliant with EOSC AAI new directives (see more here: <https://github.com/eosc-kc/keycloak>) is not matching NEANIAS project timeline.

Alternatively, and yielding equivalent results, NEANIAS opts to integrate indirectly with EOSC AAI, via an EOSC satellite AAI service, such as the *EGI CheckIn*. The latter is linked to EOSC AAI which effectively delivers the same result.

Meanwhile, NEANIAS AAI had to face the legal complexity of passing user information to the services it is being used by, in the context of a distributed infrastructure where services are operating outside the physical infrastructure of their owner. This resulted in a special "Privacy Statement" and "Terms of use" declaration that has gone under extensive legal review and is now accompanying the service for integration with an external entity (such as *EGI CheckIn*). The same set of legal documentation may be submitted to EOSC for the integration of the service, for eventual integration, which may take place within or beyond project's lifetime.

2.2.2.2. Availability and reliability monitoring

Availability monitoring is a service where users and service providers can check the status of an EOSC service and get information about its availability and reliability in the selected time period. NEANIAS services have been integrated with the ARGO monitoring platform [4] for this purpose. At the time of writing this deliverable, this integration has been completed, covering both the NEANIAS thematic services as well as the NEANIAS core services. The integration has proven valuable both to track important availability metrics, but also to track on a daily basis the status and health of the NEANIAS services, as well as to get notified on noteworthy events, contributing to the end user perceived quality of service. Furthermore, deeper integration steps with the EGI ARGO service have been pursued and selected metrics are made available at the NEANIAS Service Catalogue.

Moreover, ARGO monitoring is being complemented by the NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure, local to the GARR Cloud facilities, to allow the implementation of different types of monitoring, such as whitebox monitoring. Both services are utilized to monitor the NEANIAS services, offering different integration capabilities to the Service Providers, and allowing both internal and external monitoring to cover a wider range of metrics and troubleshooting scenarios.

2.2.2.3. Accounting

As mentioned in Deliverable D8.3 [1], NEANIAS usage accounting strategy has a substantially different perspective than the one that EOSC accounting approach captures. EOSC accounting approach targets lower-level resources such as storage, computation etc., while NEANIAS sculpts a more fine-grained approach targeting specific interactions and subproducts or entities of the usage of resources (e.g. which feature, fined-grained CPU or storage consumption association etc.). Not only that, but with the present AAI approach and its adoption by dependent technologies, it is rather difficult to effectively manage and track resource usage to the user, at all levels of an infrastructure, without application specific modelling and support of the resources. Furthermore, there are challenges pertaining to sensitive data management that substantially hinder the usability of a 3rd party service for tracking usage data.

These observations directed NEANIAS to follow a different direction regarding accounting, which has proven not only trustworthy, featureful and robust, but it also greatly assisted the project to extract significant information about the services operation, with minimal intervention to their internals.

Furthermore, NEANIAS opted to prioritize integration with the monitoring solution of EOSC, as presented in section 2.2.2.2, which is essential for service existence on EOSC, while accounting integration hasn't been a requirement.

2.2.2.4. Helpdesk

To assist and support the end users of the NEANIAS offered Services, a ticketing system has been made available, acting as the entry point for service consumers to report issues, incidents and requests in a structured fashion. This ticketing system, formally named "NEANIAS service management IT system", is the NEANIAS Helpdesk system and supports the collection of:

- Incident Reports - Unplanned disruption of operation in a service or service component, or degradation of service quality versus the expected or agreed service level or operational level.
- Service Requests - User request for information, advice, access to a service, etc.

The NEANIAS Helpdesk processes and functionality, as defined within the context of the Service Management System (Deliverable D8.2 "EOSC service model" [5]), aim to cover the NEANIAS users' needs for support and communication with the respective service providers.

Although not a mandate within the NEANIAS description of action, the opportunity to integrate the NEANIAS Helpdesk with the EOSC Helpdesk may be beneficiary for the end users in providing a more streamlined support experience. To this end, the following integration options offered from the EOSC Helpdesk can be investigated for future integration:

- Ticket Redirection: Use the EOSC helpdesk only as a contact point to redirect the entry request for the specific service to a mailing list.
- Full Integration: Integrate an external ticketing system with the EOSC helpdesk infrastructure to enable transfer of tickets between them.

2.2.3. Research Data Management

In this section we provide an overview of some of the existing EOSC services regarding FAIR data management that we opted to reuse and integrate, so that NEANIAS services are conformant with the Open Data Guidelines [6] and the FAIR principles [7]. As our project moves along and as the EOSC service portfolio expands we will also expand our view and will consider additional research data management services for integration.

2.2.3.1. ARGOS Data Management Planning tool

Argos [8] is an open and extensible EOSC service that simplifies the management, validation, monitoring and maintenance of Data Management Plans. It is a service provided by OpenAIRE, contributed by NEANIAS in its validation stage. Argos allows actors (researchers, managers, supervisors, etc.) to create actionable DMPs that may be freely exchanged among infrastructures for carrying out specific aspects of the Data management process in accordance with the intentions and commitment of Data owners. To facilitate the adoption of the platform, NEANIAS has engaged OpenAIRE experts since the beginning of the project to provide support on the use of the platform both in live presentations and as web training.

In NEANIAS, we exclusively use Argos to maintain our Data Management plans, however no integration is planned with other RDM related service in the scope of the project.

2.2.3.2. Research Data Repository

NEANIAS handles data in its own resources for processing and integrates with well-known data repositories for obtaining data of relevance to its services. Those are handled by each specific thematic service provider. Currently there are no functional requirements that direct service providers to proceed to integration with specific EOSC repositories, however the overall intent of the project to empower Open Science and FAIR data, applies a uniform policy for all its services with respect to data publication.

Zenodo [9], an EOSC core service, is the catch-all repository developed and maintained by CERN as part of the OpenAIRE project, in support of Open Science and FAIR principles. Zenodo's aim is to store all of its contents for the lifetime of the repository, providing free access to all metadata under the CC0 license (except for email addresses). Additionally, all metadata can be harvested via the OAI-PMH mechanism for repository interoperability [10]. Moreover, Zenodo offers a REST API [11] to allow applications to:

- a) upload and publish research outputs,
- b) search published records,
- c) upload and download files.

In NEANIAS, we opted to use Zenodo via its REST API for depositing all research product metadata, and for all open-access research data.

Furthermore, NEANIAS implemented a generic core service, the "Zenodo Bridge" that allows other services to easily integrate Zenodo and publish onto it directly from NEANIAS data space. The bridge allows combined programmatic and user interactive integration with Zenodo, delivering to the latter's API the data and metadata for publishing research outputs produced by a NEANIAS service. It picks those transparently from NEANIAS service storage API and allows the user to fine-tune the publication package itself, offering a web UI and allowing use of one's personal Zenodo account.

2.2.3.3. Research Data Catalogue

Data FAIRness requires that data is searchable by users, which in turn, requires that they are properly described and registered. NEANIAS uses Zenodo as its data catalogue and follows the respective metadata description specification. Furthermore, we will organize data under the “community” concept, to facilitate their attribution to the project and simplify their discovery when coming from NEANIAS origins.

2.2.3.4. PID infrastructure

Publishing data requires that those can be identified uniquely by their consumers. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are the common construct for that. In NEANIAS, all published datasets will acquire a PID, under the DOI schema. We use Zenodo as a Persistent Identifier (PID) production service to allow NEANIAS services to automatically obtain PIDs for research outputs.

2.3. Service management

As presented in Deliverable D8.2 “EOSC Service Model” [5], NEANIAS chose to develop an IT Service Management System of its own, which is nevertheless compatible with the EOSC one. More specifically, the NEANIAS SMS is developed based on the same service management framework as the EOSC one, i.e. FitSM [12], with ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018 extensions [13] (where/if needed), utilising also ITIL guidance [14] as best practice. This way, we aim on one hand to be compliant with the EOSC service management system and on the other hand to establish a more tailored-made SMS, which will better serve the needs of NEANIAS services. Additionally, we aim to have increased control on the SMS, so that we can adjust it more easily and quickly to future developments of the services and needs of the providers of NEANIAS services.

The main tools that support the NEANIAS SMS include the following:

Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS catalogue portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides the interface to service providers to register and describe their services • Presents information about the services that NEANIAS provides to users • Enables service ordering • Provides the interface to users for submitting incidents and service requests, complaints, requirements about services, etc.
NEANIAS service management IT system ¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors the lifecycle of incidents and service requests, complaints, changes, etc.
NEANIAS wiki	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system

¹ The NEANIAS service management IT system is developed under WP7 and implements a workflow-type functionality on a ticketing software platform (redmine).

The above tools are complemented by own tools of the thematic/core service providers, which focus on the more technical aspects of service management (e.g. performance monitoring, logging, event management, capacity management etc.).

2.4. Service ordering and pricing

The goal of the task was to better understand the expectations of the providers concerning order management via EOSC, and to specify the actions needed for the implementation of non-trivial ordering scenarios, for example when financial transactions are needed.

The task established the following plan: NEANIAS services are/should be accessible in EOSC via 4 ways:

1. Open access: The service does not need user authentication/authorisation and can be accessed via redirection from the EOSC Marketplace (MP). The already onboarded NEANIAS services all use this option.
2. Ordering: The service requires an access order from the user. This order is generated by the EOSC MP and sent to the NEANIAS provider who can enable access and approve the order in the MP. The NEANIAS SMS already describes this process, but there is no service yet using it.
3. Ordering with computing resources provided by the user: This would be a new option in which the user must make a compute allocation in EOSC before submitting the NEANIAS order and include the allocation endpoint in the NEANIAS order. The details are developed in collaboration with the EGI-ACE project (See below).
4. Pay-for-use ordering: This option was assessed separately and is detailed below in paragraph 2.4.1. The conclusion was that this will not be elaborated further in NEANIAS. The providers who need this should register their service with a 'demonstration access' level in EOSC. More complex access has to be negotiated bilaterally with the user outside EOSC/NEANIAS.

2.4.1. Pay-for-use ordering

At the time of writing the NEANIAS proposal it was expected that the EOSC Core Services would introduce pay-for-use (or other financial transaction) capabilities, which NEANIAS services could rely on. From interactions with the EOSC team in 2021 it was understood that the EOSC does not have pay-for-use ordering, or any other financial transaction support in its roadmap. One of the reasons for this is that the EOSC implementation roadmap puts academic, free-at-point-of-use resources in its focus until 2023; industry and other sectors are planned for only after that.

From D9.3 [15] and from discussions within the NEANIAS Consortium it was confirmed that there are a few services in NEANIAS that expect income from pay-for-use transactions beyond the project lifetime. The task organised a roundtable discussion with service providers to understand which providers and why would need pay-for-use or other financial transactions. Two reasons came out from the investigation:

1. Some of the thematic services require big capacity machines for use cases that go beyond a certain input size. Pay-for-use could be an option for those use cases to recuperate the cost of using big machines, however there could be other options, such

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as shifting the compute intensive workload to external e-infrastructures that are free-at-point-of-use for NEANIAS providers and their users.

2. Some of the thematic service providers are commercial entities and would like to provide their service on a pay-for-use basis in EOSC.

The discussion concluded that we would explore option 1 via an interaction with external e-infrastructures, particularly with the EGI-ACE project that delivers the Compute Platform in EOSC. This is detailed in the next section 2.4.2.

For option 2 the conclusion was that the implementation of a pay-for-use system within NEANIAS would require more effort than the project has, and overall is out of scope for our Description of Action. Experiences show that payments between different countries and legal entities can be complex, and involve finance, legal and technical aspects that are often unique to each institute.

2.4.2. Relying on the EOSC Compute Platform

We assessed the offering of the EOSC Compute Platform provided by EGI-ACE project (<https://www.egi.eu/projects/egi-ace/>) and found it a suitable platform to scale out the NEANIAS services that require external hosting/execution environments. Using the EGI-ACE Open Call mechanism (<https://www.egi.eu/projects/egi-ace/call-for-use-cases>) NEANIAS submitted an application to EGI-ACE by the 15th of December 2021 deadline, requesting cloud resources (CPU, GPU, storage) to setup and validate two use cases in the EOSC Compute Platform:

1. Scale out compute intensive NEANIAS thematic services to EGI-ACE cloud/Kubernetes resources. The successful validation of this use case would open a new service delivery model for NEANIAS thematic service providers: Their users would have to request compute allocations from the EOSC Compute Platform, and 'bring these allocations' to the thematic service providers who would connect these to their service to serve that individual user.
2. Hosting NEANIAS thematic services in EGI-ACE cloud/Kubernetes resources. The successful validation of this use case would open a new sustainability model for thematic service providers: The thematic service providers could make arrangements with EOSC Compute Platform providers for the hosting of the NEANIAS services beyond the NEANIAS lifetime, and delivering the services as a collaborative effort of NEANIAS and EOSC Compute Platform providers.

The successful validation of these cases would provide a new sustainability path for some of the NEANIAS services (e.g. A2 and U3 providers found this a workable approach). There are, however, cases in NEANIAS where the approach cannot be used: Some services use IP protected codebase and running them (or even part of the service) on external machines is not a viable option.

The NEANIAS application was accepted by EGI-ACE, and at the time of writing we are working under the following timeline:

- Finalise and submit the use case to EGI-ACE: 15th of December 2022
- Getting access to the EGI-ACE resources: January 2022

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- Reach first service setups with the use cases: end of July 2022
- Validation of the setups: end of August 2022
- Reach full validation with all the NEANIAS services in scope: end of September 2022 (end of use of EGI-ACE resources)
- Update NEANIAS delivery model in EOSC (incl. User guides), and sustainability models: end of October 2022

3. Status of EOSC integration activities

In this section we present the results of EOSC integration activities as these were realised by the time of writing this document.

3.1. Onboarding of NEANIAS services to EOSC

NEANIAS activities towards EOSC integration followed an agile approach based on successive development cycles, according to the plan initially presented in Deliverable D8.1 [16] and then verified and amended where appropriate in Deliverable D8.3 [2]. The EOSC integration plan considers the following:

- The cycles bring NEANIAS services from very basic EOSC integration with minimal functionalities to more complex EOSC integration with advanced capabilities.
- We specify the exact content for each cycle considering the situation at that moment when we reach that cycle.
- The cycles can be repeated for the different Thematic Services independently from each other. For example, cycle 1 can start for the most mature thematic service as soon as that thematic service is ready for publication in EOSC. Other thematic services will be considered for cycle 1 once they become mature enough for EOSC.
- Cycle 1 as well as cycle 2 has a set of preparatory steps that NEANIAS should complete before any of the thematic services reach those cycles. These preparatory steps should be completed only one time, while the cycles should be completed one time for each thematic service.

The main accomplishments towards EOSC integration per cycle of the EOSC integration plan of Deliverable D8.3 [2] include:

Preparatory steps for cycle 1 (done once) [Started at M3; Finished at M22]

The preparatory steps for cycle 1 have been completed before the elaboration of Deliverable D8.3 in M22, therefore two (2) months ahead of the initially envisaged timeline (where these steps were due in M24):

- NEANIAS catalogue portal was developed, deployed, and populated with information on NEANIAS providers and services.
- Terms of Use and Privacy Policy skeletons were developed, in order to be reused and customized by each NEANIAS service during EOSC onboarding.
- NEANIAS Service Management System was defined in D8.2; Tools supporting the operation of the NEANIAS Service Management System were defined (see Section 2.3), and are continuously evolving according to the needs of the NEANIAS services.

Cycle 1 – Make NEANIAS thematic services accessible to EOSC users by following the EOSC onboarding process (done for each thematic service)

Cycle 1 activities started at M12 and are still in progress for each thematic service independently, following the maturity of each service. Although initially planned for

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completion by M31, the need to resolve legal issues related to the integration of EOSC and NEANIAS AAI (related to the presence of appropriate the terms of use and privacy statements), as well as to address changes on EOSC marketplace that impact its integration with the NEANIAS catalogue portal, required the extension of the schedule for these activities. However, this extension did not have any impact on making the thematic services available on EOSC. The main accomplishments include:

- EOSC Provider and Resource profiles were used for Providers and Service modelling, in order to facilitate the onboarding of NEANIAS providers and services in the EOSC portal and comply with the existing standards and EOSC guidelines.
- Service levels and related information were addressed in the Terms of Use of each service.
- An access request mechanism has been developed on the NEANIAS SMS and may be used by NEANIAS services on EOSC that require some type of registration/authorization. This mechanism is maintained and updated, based on the needs of NEANIAS services. Currently all NEANIAS services available on EOSC marketplace are open access, thus not requiring the use of an ordering mechanism.
- Helpdesk support is available for the users of the services in the form of a helpdesk e-mail and/or using the NEANIAS helpdesk system to submit requests, incidents, complaints, etc.

Preparatory steps for cycle 2 (done once)

The preparatory steps for cycle 2 included the completion of the following activities:

- The NEANIAS research product catalogue based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform was released; we have created a community named "NEANIAS" for the NEANIAS research products on Zenodo.
- The NEANIAS PID service based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform was released; PIDs are provided as part of the usual CERN (Zenodo provider) publishing process.
- The NEANIAS Data Validation Service has been redesigned to better address the needs of the users.
- For the NEANIAS Data Publishing Service, a component that facilitates publishing to Zenodo was released in Q1 2022.
- NEANIAS was integrated with OpenDMP deployed on OpenAIRE as Argos; NEANIAS is contributing, being among the first pilot projects for it.

Cycle 2 – Enrich NEANIAS services with research product catalogue and data management capabilities (done for each thematic service)

Cycle 2 activities are an option for thematic services and each one independently can progress to embrace any or all of the offerings, depending on the need and relevance of the offering and the maturity of each service. In this context, the main activities performed include:

- Integration with the NEANIAS research product catalogue and the NEANIAS PID service based on OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform is good practice but not mandatory for NEANIAS services. To facilitate integration, the Zenodo REST API was presented and

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demonstrated. Additionally, services that integrate with the Data Publishing Service can obtain a PID this way. Utilizing the Zenodo Bridge component is an option offered at the later stage of the project for services to utilize.

- Integration with the NEANIAS Data Publishing Service is investigated by each service provider, according to the requirements of its service. Integration with the service is good practice but not mandatory for NEANIAS services.
- No programmatic integration with the NEANIAS Data Validation Service or with OpenDMP deployed on OpenAIRE as Argos was considered as both integrations are optional for NEANIAS services and users can exploit the DVS or Argos independently after publishing data from thematic services.

Cycle 3 – Improve support for EOSC users based on initial experiences (done for each thematic service)

Cycle 3 activities are in progress for each thematic service independently and follow the maturity of each service. In this context, the main activities performed include:

- FAQs, manual, software documentation and similar information about the services are presented on the webpages of each service and constantly updated; the kind and the extent of information published for each service depend on the characteristics of the service and the service support requirements deemed necessary by the respective service provider.
- NEANIAS usage accounting and monitoring services have been activated. Before EOSC onboarding, service providers select how they integrate with these services, according to their accounting and monitoring requirements. However, the integration is not a prerequisite for EOSC onboarding.
- Integration of NEANIAS Services with EOSC Availability and Reliability monitoring was achieved, according to the needs and requirements of the providers of the services. At the time of writing this deliverable, eleven (11) thematic and sixteen (16) core services were already integrated with EOSC Availability and Reliability monitoring.

On the other hand:

- NEANIAS usage accounting was not integrated with EOSC Accounting, as NEANIAS usage accounting strategy has a substantially different perspective than the one that EOSC main accounting offering captures (see also 2.2.2.3).
- No support for customised SLAs and OLAs was provided as no such needs were identified based on the characteristics of the services.

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Based on the above, the overall achievements of EOSC onboarding activities are shown in the following table.

Service name	Lead Provider	Onboarding status
THEMATIC SERVICES		
Underwater services		
U1 - Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data	TELEDYNE	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/uw-bat
U2 - Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data	CORONIS	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/uw-mos
U3 - Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data	ATHENA	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/uw-map
Atmosphere services		
A1 – Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring	ATHENA	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/atmo-flud
A2 – Monitor atmospheric Perturbations and Components in Active Tectonic Regions		
<i>Atmo-Stress</i>	ATHENA	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/atmo-stress
<i>Atmo-Seism</i>	ATHENA	This service won't be integrated but will be accessed through NEANIAS and Atmo-Stress EOSC service
A3 – Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting	UBIWHERE	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/atmo-4cast
Space services		
S1 - FAIR Data Management and Visualization for Complex Data and Metadata		
<i>SPACE-VIS ViaLactea Service</i>	INAF	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/space-vis-vialactea-service
<i>SPACE-VIS ADN Service</i>	ALTEC	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/space-vis-adn-service

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Service name	Lead Provider	Onboarding status
<i>ADAM-SPACE</i>	MEE0	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/adam-space
S2 - Map making and mosaicing for multidimensional image	MEE0	N/A. These are Backend Service functionalities exposed through and accessed from the Vialactea and ADAM-SPACE services.
S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques		
<i>SPACE-ML CAESAR service</i>	INAF	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/space-ml-caesar-service
<i>SPACE-ML AstroML service</i>	INAF	N/A. These are Deep Learning models included and accessed by the SPACE-ML CAESAR service and also made available through the C3.1 AI Science Gateway.
<i>SPACE-ML LSE service</i>	UNIMIB	In progress
CORE SERVICES		
C2 Artificial Intelligence services		
Data Exploration Service (ADAM Platform)	MEE0	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/adam-platform
C3 Artificial Intelligence services		
C3.1 AI Science Gateway	SZTAKI	N/A
C3.2 Serving trained ML models	ALTEC	N/A
C3.3 Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod	SZTAKI	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/distributed-deep-learning-by-horovod
C3.4 Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML	UNIMIB	Under investigation
C4 Visualisation services		
C4.1 Framework for Visual Discovery (VD)		

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Service name	Lead Provider	Onboarding status
<i>VD-VisIVO</i>	INAF	N/A. Integrated in C4.2 Visualisation Gateway and onboarding process depends on that service.
<i>VD-Splotch</i>	UoP	N/A. Integrated in C4.2 Visualisation Gateway and onboarding process depends on that service.
<i>VD-Maps</i>	CORONIS	Onboarded https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/vd-maps
C4.2 Visualisation Gateway (VG)	UoP	N/A. The service will not be onboarded to EOSC.
C4.3 Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR)	ALTEC	N/A
C4.4 Spatial Data Stores (DS)	JACOBS	N/A

At the time of writing this document, ten (10) thematic services (TRL7 or greater) have already been made available in EOSC marketplace and the onboarding of one more is in progress. Additionally, three (3) core services (TRL8 and 9) have been onboarded to EOSC and the onboarding of one more is under investigation.

Comparing the current status against the one presented in D8.4, we note the following:

- The number of NEANIAS thematic services on EOSC marketplace has increased by **four**. More specifically the following additional services have been onboarded to EOSC:
 - U1 - Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data
 - Atmo-Stress under A2 – Monitor atmospheric Perturbations and Components in Active Tectonic Regions
 - A3 – Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting
 - SPACE-VIS ADN Service under S1 - FAIR Data Management and Visualization for Complex Data and Metadata
- **One additional** thematic service (SPACE-ML LSE service under S3 - Structure detection on large map images with machine learning techniques) will soon be available in EOSC marketplace as the onboarding process is in progress. This is a new service in the Space sector, not accounted for in D8.4, as it was first introduced around the time of writing D8.4.
- Atmo-Seism service under A2 – Monitor atmospheric Perturbations and Components in Active Tectonic Regions will not finally be onboarded to EOSC. However, it will be accessed through NEANIAS and Atmo-Stress EOSC service.

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As for the onboarding of NEANIAS core services to EOSC, the following developments are noted (additional to the ones described in D8.4):

- One C3 core service (C3.3 Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod) has been onboarded to EOSC in Q1 2022 according to the plan presented in Deliverable in D8.4.
- Although the EOSC onboarding of C1 and C2 services was not considered at the beginning of NEANIAS project, the Data Exploration Service (ADAM Platform) under C2 “Artificial Intelligence services” was made available in EOSC marketplace.
- The onboarding of one additional core service (C3.4 Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML) with EGI resources is under investigation. At the time of writing this deliverable, NEANIAS team is working with the respective EGI team to address technical details for the realisation of this scenario. At the same time, the C3.4 service provider is exploring the EOSC Marketplace to see whether similar services already exist on it in order to reach a final decision for the onboarding of the service to EOSC.
- VD-VisIVO and VD-Splotch services are integrated in C4.2 Visualisation Gateway, therefore their onboarding to EOSC depends on C4.2. As the C4.2 service will not be onboarded to EOSC, VD-VisIVO and VD-Splotch service functionality will not be made available to EOSC users either.

3.2. Integration with EOSC services

The following table presents up-to-date information on the integration/ connection of NEANIAS (core) services with EOSC equivalent/ relevant ones:

EOSC service areas	NEANIAS Service	Status / Comments
1. EOSC Portal	NEANIAS catalogue portal	<p>Completed and constantly updated based on EOSC developments.</p> <p>The interoperability of the NEANIAS catalogue portal with the EOSC one through the EOSC API (v3.0 and EOSC Profiles v3.0) has been completed. Through this integration, changes applied by providers on services in the NEANIAS catalogue portal are propagated and made available in the EOSC marketplace. In the next period changes will occur due to EOSC catalogue transition</p>

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EOSC service areas		NEANIAS Service	Status / Comments
			<p>to profile v4.00. Changes will also affect NEANIAS catalogue:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addition of the abbreviation field to resources • Use cases and multimedia must have two fields (description and URL field) • HLE will get vocabulary values instead of free text • New vocabularies for multiple entries • Addition of the field catalogue id at both providers and resources. Catalogue id is a mandatory new field at EOSC, declaring the catalogue at which the entry was first hosted. <p>In addition to the above mentioned implementations, the integration of NEANIAS catalogue portal with the ARGOS monitoring system has been achieved. This way, users are able to see in real time the status of the services (e.g. available or not).</p>
2.Federation services	EOSC AAI (directly or indirectly by satellite AAI, such as EGI CheckIn)	NEANIAS AAI	Applied for EGI Check In and waiting, for service configuration to be delivered by EGI.
	Availability and reliability monitoring	NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure	<p>The integration of EOSC monitoring with NEANIAS thematic and core services is ongoing.</p> <p>The NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure is being used to complement EOSC monitoring with support for, e.g., whitebox monitoring.</p>

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EOSC service areas		NEANIAS Service	Status / Comments
	Usage accounting (service usage, compute, storage etc.)	NEANIAS Accounting	No integration is currently planned.
	Helpdesk (ticketing system)	NEANIAS Helpdesk system	No interface. NEANIAS will use its own Helpdesk system. Integration to be revisited in the future.
3. Research data management services	Compute, storage, transfer, analysis, etc.)	GARR Cloud	No integration is currently planned in NEANIAS.
	Zenodo (research output catalogue + PID)	Service Catalogue Research Data Repository and Catalogue Data Management based on ARGOS	Argos is integrated with Zenodo.
4. Service Management System (SMS)	EOSC SMS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service management processes defined using FitSM • Respective implementation tools 	NEANIAS SMS defined in D8.2 [5]: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service management processes and procedures defined using FitSM • Implementation tools defined and developed (Section 2.3 and D8.2) 	Although separate than the EOSC SMS, the NEANIAS SMS was developed following the same principles and framework as the EOSC one.
5. Service pricing: Pay-for-use ordering	No pay-for-use ordering, or any other financial transaction support, in EOSC's current or envisaged offerings	---	To be investigated by service providers outside of NEANIAS project

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EOSC service areas		NEANIAS Service	Status / Comments
6. Service pricing: Ordering with computing resources provided by the user	EOSC Compute Platform provided by EGI-ACE project	---	In the process of using EOSC Compute Platform based on the plan presented in section 2.4.2

4. Conclusions

Since the first release of EOSC integration plan in Deliverable D8.1 in July 2020 and its reviews and updates in Deliverables D8.3 [2] (August 2021) and D8.4 [1] (December 2021), a lot of developments both at the EOSC level and at NEANIAS services have been realised. As derived from the information presented in Chapter 3, the integration of NEANIAS with EOSC is progressing quite smoothly, has produced significant results, and has already met (and exceeded) the targets initially set. More specifically:

1. Ten (10) thematic services (TRL7 or greater) have already onboarded EOSC, while another one is expected to become available on EOSC marketplace in the July 2022. This way, the project has already exceeded its target to onboard nine (9) thematic services to EOSC.
2. Providers of NEANIAS core services have further processed and clarified their plans for EOSC onboarding; three (3) core services are already available on EOSC marketplace, and the onboarding of an additional one is under investigation.
3. NEANIAS core services have already been aligned with EOSC ones in the areas of AAI, accounting, monitoring. Moreover, the integration of NEANIAS Research Data Management services with corresponding EOSC ones is already providing the platform to thematic services for bringing FAIR data onto EOSC.
4. The NEANIAS service management system has been defined and made available to all NEANIAS service providers for application. On top, a helpdesk system has been setup and customised in order to support the execution of the processes and procedures defined by the NEANIAS SMS. Services that go through the process of EOSC onboarding are expected to be integrated with the helpdesk system.
5. The project has already completed the integration of NEANIAS catalogue portal with EOSC marketplace through the use of the EOSC API. In the remaining project duration, this integration is to be further enhanced in order to fully exploit the new features associated with the transition of EOSC catalogue to profile v4.00.

As EOSC integration is a continuously evolving challenge, NEANIAS will stay open for new integration opportunities offered by EOSC until the end of the project.

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